

**Strategic people management in contemporary highly dynamic VUCA contexts:
A knowledge worker perspective¹²**

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ABSTRACT

This paper extends the resource and knowledge-based view by integrating dynamic capability theory into a people-centric view of the firm in new and highly dynamic contexts. Juxtaposing people management and human resource management, we commend people centrality for knowledge management and dynamic capability formation within a context of highly dynamic environments induced not only by disruptive technology, unpredictable crisis, and high-velocity emerging markets but augmented through simultaneous multilevel crises events. For these contexts, we propose a novel and holistic framework of strategic people management that incorporates four dynamic constituents - leadership, culture, learning, networking - that help to acquire, transfer and create knowledge relevant for firm's sustainability. These unbundled constituents interact to create a systematic effect and co-evolve with firm's dynamic capabilities. The paper conceptually contributes with its emphasis on people-centricity as the infinity source of valuable, rare, inimitable, and organizational resources, such as knowledge workers to continuously create, transfer, convert, and manage knowledge flows.

Keywords: Knowledge based view, VUCA context, people management, knowledge management, strategic human resource management, dynamic environment

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1. INTRODUCTION

The well-grounded paradigm of the resource-based view (RBV) of the firm is still one of the most influential and successful theories in the field of management (Cooper, Pereira, Vrontis & Liu, 2020; Nason & Wiklund, 2018). However, both RBV and its extended knowledge-based view (KBV) research are less applied to the nowadays context of highly dynamic environments characterized by volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA) (Pereira & Bamel, 2021). We aim to theoretically extend the line of RBV and KBV research by incorporating the knowledge worker perspective to humanize strategy (Nonaka, 1994; Nonaka & Takeuchi, 2021). When knowledge is incorporated into a firm's strategic competitive position with the dynamic theory of internal resources and capabilities (Grant, 2016; Spender, 1996), scholars find the dominant research theme that considers "strategy as plan" becomes increasingly troublesome in a highly dynamic context, due to the difficulty to foresee and apply existing patterns in a context of environmental uncertainty (Bindra et al., 2019; Teece, 2020).

With this dilemma, the call for further debate and application of RBV and KBW to new contemporary contexts such as volatile and complex transitional emerging markets, technology-intensive industries with fast-changing pace, and imminent and enduring pandemic-induced business environment (Cooper et al., 2020), is timely. Global businesses experience highly dynamic contexts with technological advancements such as artificial intelligence and digitalization, and the rising power of emerging economies (Li & Liu, 2014; Sinkovics, Yamin,

Nadvi & Zhang-Zhang, 2014; Teece, 2020). Additionally, simultaneous multilevel crisis events such as the COVID-19 pandemic corroborates the even more increasingly VUCA contexts. They bring higher levels of dynamism into management and organization as these crisis events occur not only immediately leaving little planning time to managers but are also uncertainty sustained. To achieve firms' competitive sustainability within such a highly dynamic and uncertain context, a paradoxical balance between strategy planning and human creativity is critical (Zhang-Zhang & Varma, 2020), paving the path for the people-centricity view of the firm with knowledge workers and the knowledge of the firm managed to provide options for alternative dynamic capabilities in new but uncertain dynamic markets in the future (Kogut & Zander, 1992; Pereira et al., 2019).

In this paper, we take a novel approach to explore strategic people management (SPM) founded on the KBV-based premise that people are knowledge workers (Nonaka, 1991; Zhang, Zhou & McKenzie, 2013), specifically in highly dynamic VUCA contexts, where their creativity, ingenuity, and knowledge generation can contribute in unique ways to an organization's bottom-line. As an extension of RBV-grounded strategic human resource management (HRM), SPM proposes a holistic framework to demonstrate the strategic contributions of people management from a knowledge perspective to firm's sustainable development and longevity in a new highly dynamic VUCA context. By extending the RBV-premised human resource function to the conceptualization of people from a knowledge worker perspective, we are able to explore the dynamic people management capabilities to drive strategic directions in a highly dynamic business environment.

The paper proceeds as follows. Next, we review the theoretical evolution of RBV to KBV, and the importance of strategically managing knowledge workers in new and highly dynamic VUCA contexts for strategic sustainability. Juxtaposing then HRM and people

management illuminates the understanding of SPM to act in a business ecosystem and to help capability development rather than being solely focused on job-based functionality and the inner-organizational context. In section 4, we propose a framework of SPM consisting of four dynamic drivers of knowledge sources aiding firm's sustainability in a highly dynamic VUCA context. We then outline the theoretical contributions and future research lines before offering final remarks.

2. NEW HIGHLY DYNAMIC VUCA CONTEXTS, RBV & KBV, AND PEOPLE-CENTRICITY

Dynamic environments per se have been commonly reflected by scholars and practitioners in management studies. A swift search in ScienceDirect with “dynamic environments” on June 8th 2021 identified 3,050 results in the subject areas of Business, Management and Accounting; and 257 results in *Journal of Business Research* (JBR) alone. A brief review on the results in JBR sorted by relevance found the majority of papers have borrowed dynamic environments as a context for their studies but this is often without any explicit definition. A few exceptions are Adomako (2021: 479) who characterizes a dynamic environment “by frequent changes, leading to unpredictability and high levels of uncertainty” based on Dess and Beard (1984); or Katou, Budhwar and Patel (2021: 692) who refer to environmental dynamism as “the degree of continuous and intensive changes” based on Jansen, Van den Bosch and Volberda (2006). Dynamic environments are frequently associated with change (Adomako, 2021; Glyptis et al., 2021), competitiveness (Jansen et al., 2006; Katou et al., 2021), volatility (Wu, 2010), uncertainty and unpredictability (Adomako, 2021; Dess & Beard, 1984), complexity (D’Innocenzo et al., 2016), and ambiguity (Hansen, Güttel & Swart, 2019) and therefore resemble closely the concept of VUCA contexts.

Nowadays, organizations encounter new challenges sparked by a uniquely high degrees of volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity. Contemporary environments tend to contain a certain level of dynamism, often differentiated into high-velocity/highly volatile/highly dynamic environments and moderately dynamic markets (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Wu, 2010). Current environments have gained an extra degree of volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity prompted by simultaneous and multiple phenomena and thus constitute new unique contexts with high dynamism. Over the last decade, organizations were not only challenged by disruptive innovation from technology advancements, accelerated nowadays through digitalization and artificial intelligence (e.g., García-Villaverde, Rodrigo-Alarcón, Parra-Requena & Ruiz-Ortega, 2018), but also by complex emerging market players which are growing, developing and transiting at a rapid pace and challenge Western dominance (Li, Easterby-Smith & Hong, 2019; Malik, Sharma, Pereira, & Temouri, 2021; Qaiyum & Wang, 2018). These heightened dynamics are currently further intensified by the simultaneous unpredictability caused by the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak (Zhang-Zhang & Varma, 2020) or significant economic downturns (Hansen et al., 2019). Furthermore, a cross-level dynamism is provoked by multiple phenomena that jointly produce highly dynamic VUCA contexts, e.g., joint industry/country effects with technology at industrial level and emerging markets at country level (Fletcher-Brown, Carter, Pereira, & Chandwani, 2021; Malik, Pereira, & Budhwar, 2021; Zhang-Zhang, Rohlfer, & Rajasekera, 2020). This new context of highly dynamic environments is unprecedented.

How is the RBV and KBV then applied and extended in these new contemporary contexts with high dynamism? (Pereira & Bamel, 2021). Knowledge indeed plays a critical role in highly dynamic VUCA contexts beyond knowledge accessibility (García-Villaverde et al., 2018; Tushman, 1979) which is a common question in a relatively stable environment. Within dynamic environments, the knowledge of causes and effects of phenomena is uncertain, and

existing efficiency and effectiveness measures may be inappropriate (Covaleski & Dirsmith, 1981). Thus, new knowledge is needed to rapidly create new dynamic capabilities and reconfigure existing resources and capabilities for change (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Glyptis et al., 2021). Especially high-tech firms are knowledge-intensive and mainly dependent on human resources for value creation (Qaiyum & Wang, 2018). This is equally true for high-velocity emerging markets where dynamic capabilities extensively rely on new knowledge combined from global and local ones (Li et al., 2019), and for crisis' induced complex dynamic incidences when HRM systems are seen as “knowledge-governance mechanisms of human capital and organizational capabilities” for different learning modes (Hansen et al., 2019: 652).

Grounded in Penrose (1959), an internal resources and capabilities view of the firm (Wernerfelt, 1984; Rumelt, 1984), the RBV, was popularized by Barney (1991) and has risen to dominate the field of strategy. This paradigmatic shift is extended by further theoretical development of a knowledge-based view of the firm (Nonaka, 1991; Kogut & Zander, 1992) and dynamic capabilities (Teece et al., 1997), among others. Founded on RBV and KBV, knowledge is also the base of a dynamic theory of the firm (Spender, 1996). Among different lines of knowledge management, mainly distinguished by focusing knowledge system based on information technology or emphasizing people system as knowledge workers (Alavi & Leidner, 2001), we take the latest thinking of Nonaka and Takeuchi (2021) on knowledge with a human-centric approach to further extend the resource and knowledge-based view in the new contexts of highly dynamic VUCA environments. Specifically, we focus on people-centricity, i.e., a knowledge worker perspective (Zhang et al., 2013). From the emphasis on tacit knowledge to *phronesis* or practical wisdom, individuals have always been the center of attention as knowledge resides in them (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 2021). Saying so, all knowledge is necessary, not only at the top of the organization as its authority base, but also at lower-level employees who deal with uncertainties which cannot be resolved by senior management (Spender, 1996).

Thus, both human resources at top and lower levels need to be involved in strategizing processes to participate in knowledge creation and diffusion to learn and transform the firm, especially in an open and dynamic context (Liu & Zhang, 2014; Spender, 1996).

The field of management undergoes major paradigm shifts responding to the economic changes at large (Spender, 1996). While the RBV and KBV have been applied to different research streams which in turn re-shape and re-conceptualize the two; recently these are found less applied in new contexts such as innovation strategies in emerging and transitional markets or disruptive technologies like big data or artificial intelligence (Cooper et al., 2020; Pereira & Bamel, 2021). Spender (1996) suggests questioning the definition of ‘resource’, ‘service’, ‘knowledge’, ‘knowledge-creation’, relevant social and economic entities and institutions, ‘organizational learning’, and the relationship between employees as independent agents with shareholders and others to build a viable knowledge-based theory of the firm. With the recognition of knowledge as a distinctive strategic factor of production and people as knowledge workers (Nonaka, 1991), either as employees, entrepreneurs, leaders, or managers, become the center of attention for knowledge creation and transfer across the individual-organizational level (Zhang et al., 2013).

To achieve a dynamic, evolving and quasi-autonomous system of knowledge (Spender, 1996) under the KBV, people as the embedded body of knowledge and know-how constitute a critical segment for firm’s core competences, organizational learning (McDonnel, Gunnigle, Lavelle, & Lamare, 2016) and sustainable development. The mere existence of accumulated bundles of specific human resources is insufficient to sustain firm competitive advantage in the new context of high volatility environment (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece et al., 1997; Wu, 2010). Knowledge workers or their related resources and capabilities are the ultimate internal rare, valuable and inimitable resources and capabilities which can be organized, continuously renew strategy and become the source of sustainable competitive advantage (Barney, 1991;

Grant, 2016). It is imperative to approach these resources and capabilities from a dynamic perspective in the new context of a highly dynamic environment, proactively positioning people as the original source for creating and sustaining competitive advantage (Zhang, Dolan, Lingham & Altman, 2009).

3. DYNAMIC CAPABILITIES, PEOPLE AND HUMAN RESOURCE

MANAGEMENT

Fluctuating dynamic environments, high level of unpredictability, rapid and disruptive changes lead to high level of uncertainty and accompanied ambiguity, volatility, and risk (Miller, 2007; Adomako, 2021). In such an environment, scholars often refer dynamic capabilities to overcome these challenges to reconfigure and reintegrate the unique resources, to safeguard firm's sustainability and growth (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Glyptis et al., 2021; Teece, 2007). While researchers have recognized dynamic capabilities as a universal concept (Li & Liu, 2014), the nature and evaluation of a firm's dynamic capabilities can be described in terms of people resource and that the ability to create, integrate, transfer and use people on an ongoing basis underpins firm's capabilities and competitive advantages (Teece, 1998). In a new context of highly dynamic environments, the underlying elements for the evolving dynamic capabilities are the new knowledge creation in a more rapid and unstable processes through the coevolution of past experience, low frequency knowledge articulation and knowledge codification (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Zollo & Winter, 2002). The cognitive processes of people are involved, and strong social capital and capabilities of entrepreneurs are needed to be developed (Adomako, 2021; Festing & Eidems, 2011; García-Villaverde et al., 2018).

Some scholars attempt to investigate dynamic capabilities in association with specific HRM areas, e.g., Festing and Eidems (2011) with transnational HRM systems, Garavan, Shanahan, Carbery and Watson (2016) on strategic human resource development capabilities,

Harsch and Festing (2020) on dynamic talent management capabilities, Helfat and Martin (2015) on dynamic managerial capabilities, and Verreyne, Hine, Coote and Parker (2016) on dynamic learning capabilities. An organization's human resources can be the change initiators and innovators for new knowledge creation in a fast-moving VUCA environment like COVID-19 or high-velocity emerging markets (Zhang-Zhang & Varma, 2020; Zhang et al., 2009). While Priem & Butler (2001) lament that most RBV literature has been static in concept, there are also critiques on the term 'human resources' because human beings are perceived as a static resource or asset albeit all efforts to dynamize it. For instance, Hansen et al. (2019) state that only a few studies show how human resource architectures and systems are useful in a crisis or turbulent and complex environments (e.g., Huang & Kim, 2013; Nijssen & Paauwe, 2012). In this sense, some early work to incorporate RBV to strategic HRM like Wright, Dunford and Snell (2001) through dynamic capabilities and the KBV, already brings the term of people management practices to the front. More recently, Wright and Ulrich (2017) have also frequently used the term people interchangeable with human resources in their review of the strategic HRM journey although the former has not been explicitly conceptualized. Indeed, people management has risen to provide broader and more inclusive meaning integrating different perspectives.

A brief check on the rise of people management in practice is evidenced by a search on Google on December 2nd, 2020. The keyword "human resource management" gave a result of 1,410,000,000 items, while "people management" provided 4,300,000,000 results. If narrowing the search to "business school department of human resource management" and "business school department of people management", the results showed 844,000,000 and 1,560,000,000 respectively. Yet, in academic research HRM is still the dominant term among management scholars compared to people management. A search of "people management" and "human resource management" in the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection results in 13,001 vs. 635

entries respectively. It follows that nowadays people management is more widely deployed in general practice as well as in business school departments, but less conceptualized and studied in academic terms.

However, there is a less clear definition on what people management is, and how to incorporate it into strategic management processes of an organization, albeit the people-centricity from a knowledge worker perspective based on the knowledge school was founded by Nonaka (1991) early on. We attempt to accentuate on distinguishing people management and HRM for the further RBV and KBV theoretical extension in a new dynamic VUCA context. We discover two types of relationship between people management and HRM from the WoS search results. One is the indifferent usage of these two terms by scholars in their work (e.g., Alagaraja et al., 2015; Wilkinson, Wood & Demirbag, 2014), and another is the interconnected but differentiated approach to these two terms (e.g., Purcell & Hutchison, 2007; Knies et al., 2018). Table 1 categorizes their relationships into the following quadrants along with the potential for theoretical advancement.

Insert Table 1 about here

We identify four categories of relationships between people management and HRM: progressive, old wine-new bottle, prospective and differentiator. Some early literature uses people management as being identical with HRM where the latter represents a theoretical advancement from personnel management (Caldwell, 2002; Stockard, 1980) which we term as progressive. Later developments on people management and HRM are of mixed pattern. Some scholars continue using people management as interchangeable with HRM by giving a fresh label to traditional HRM practices (old wine – new bottle). In this case scholars often use people management in the title, but the main content or literature review refers to HRM with few mentions of people management in the text again (e.g., Alagaraja et al., 2015; Wilkinson et al.,

2014). Others implicitly or explicitly distinguished people management from HRM, which prospectively offers a theoretical advancement, though their interconnection is strong and largely being an extension of the existing paradigm. Examples are Saini and Budhwar's (2008) applying people management in an emerging market SME's business context, and Purcell and Hutchinson's (2007) and Knies et al.'s (2018) extending the business partner role of HR professionals to line managers via the devolution of HR practices. A few scholars tried to differentiate people management conceptually from HRM, like Jolink and Dankbaar's (2010) intent to go beyond traditional HRM to foster organizational networking and Cabrera and Cabrera (2005) who specify people management practices to foster knowledge sharing.

By acknowledging the differentiating features of people management and traditional HRM, we reposition people management to fall within the "differentiator" quadrant by conceptualizing it with a broader meaning to manage people within and beyond the organizational boundary to achieve sustainable performance of the firm. This amplified definition is important for knowledge management and the formation of dynamic capabilities, as the target audience and action subjects of people management are managers and stakeholders in general. By contrast, HRM focuses on human resource professionals and departments and acts on managers and employees, largely limited to the internal organizational context. This distinction provides an opportunity for people management to act in a business ecosystem with an open innovation perspective for knowledge acquisition, creation, transfer, and diffusion, rather than being restricted within organizations, such as Wright et al.'s (2001) refrained people management practices on staffing, work design and so on. Table 2 illustrates the differences of the two terms with reference to management philosophy, conceptualization, strategic orientation, target audience, key actors, subject of action, dynamic capability elements, and organizational contexts.

Insert Table 2 about here

People management is less directly managerial focused than HRM in its search for short-term financial performance, but more sustainability oriented with environmental and social concerns (Alvares & de Souza, 2016; Marsilio & Prenestini, 2020). Consequently, a people-centricity principle in the management philosophy could focus more on capability development rather than job-based functionality. Though HR scholars have started reinventing HRM to make it more sustainable, note for instance Aust et al.'s (2020) common good HRM and European scholars' broader defined and inclusive HRM concept, we restrict our understanding to traditional HRM in this comparison. Within this proposed frame of people management, our interest is to extend the RBV and KBV by studying people from a knowledge worker perspective in a new open dynamic context with networking and knowledge management (e.g., Cabrera & Cabrera, 2005; Jolink & Dankbaar, 2010).

4. STRATEGIC PEOPLE MANAGEMENT: FOUR PRINCIPAL CONSTITUENTS

Different from the traditionally established strategic HRM domain of inquiry (Jackson, Schuler & Jiang, 2014; Jiang, Takeuchi & Lepak, 2013), SPM broadly focuses on people as knowledge workers as reflected in the set of management philosophy, conceptualization and the other dimensions shown above. While strategic HRM scholars are not fully satisfied with the field's progress (Jackson et al., 2014), academics have urged strategic HRM to remain sensitive to shifts in the business environment in order to continue to thrive. "Context" thus becomes an increasingly relevant factor (Farndale & Paauwe, 2018; Mayrhofer, Gooderham & Brewster, 2019) and environmental dynamism has been accepted as a central contingency variable in strategic HRM theorizing (Aust et al., 2020; Jackson et al., 2014), but remains still much criticized for its strategic fallacy (Jackson et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2009). The underlying

reasons for such fallacy might be the lack of a people management perspective to explicitly bridge between knowledge workers, business dynamism and ecosystems to smoothly form and transform dynamic capabilities in new contexts of high dynamism prompted by disruptive technologies and high velocity emerging market competition coupled with simultaneous multilevel crisis events.

People management is more oriented to people-centric organizational leaders with a focus on a broader business and more strategic context (Sparrow, Hird & Cooper, 2015), thereby offering them two additional roles for dynamic capabilities creation: a strategic decision-making role as top management sets strategic knowledge and learning oriented direction and adds value (Teece, 2020) and a policy delivery role as leadership influences employees' attitudes and behavior and gives direction (Purcell & Hutchinson, 2007) through culture and social capital network. Based on the works of Cabrera and Cabrera (2005), Goncalves et al. (2017), Jolink and Danbaar (2010), and Wright et al. (2001), we extract four elements as core practices of people management from a knowledge worker perspective to function in the new dynamic context: leadership, culture, learning, and networking. We consider people management to function more effectively in a highly dynamic context where Zhang et al. (2009) evidence that a holistic vision and dynamic approach is more helpful for strategic direction setting than a specialist perspective.

Leaders as strategic decision makers play a critical role in the interplay between people, knowledge and strategy. As strategists they are “nodes of imaginative leadership and influence in the complex of heterogeneous emotionally and politically charged knowledge systems which comprise our socially constructed reality” (Spender, 1996: 60). Culture is proposed by Cabrera and Cabrera (2005) as a key people management element for knowledge sharing, though it has already been emphasized earlier as a source of sustained competitive advantage for being

valuable, rare and imperfectly imitable (Barney, 1986: 658), in fostering firms' innovativeness and flexibility. In a new dynamic and open environment, networking has also been addressed as critical for knowledge sharing and transfer (Dyer & Nobeoka, 2000; Jackson et al., 2014), with learning as knowledge internalization process (Chirico & Salvato, 2016; Liu, Zhang-Zhang & Ghauri, 2020) and a strategic element in dynamic emerging markets (Zhang et al., 2009). Figure 1 exhibits the proposed framework of SPM for knowledge-based firms to perform in VUCA contexts.

Insert Figure 1 about here

4.1. Leadership

In a highly dynamic and turbulent environment, it is hard to rely on traditional methods to spot and capitalize on emerging threats and opportunities. Firms need to largely rely on activities – sense, organize, capture, and renew – to realize dynamic capabilities and perform, and leaders execute these activities to make it happens (Teece, 2020). As a strategic people component in management, leaders need to scan, monitor and proffer internal and external changes and development (e.g., technology, business model) to sense and seize capabilities, judge direction and dynamically manage the process (Garvin, 2002; Lopez-Cabrales et al., 2017; Teece, 2007).

Additionally, leaders are change agents and facilitators (Garvin, 2002; Teece, 2020) to trigger strategic alternatives formulation for performance, to establish goals, values, and expectations, and to motivate employees and other stakeholders (Zhu, Chew, & Spangler, 2005; Jackson et al., 2014). Leaders' perceptions of environmental dynamics, visions, and values change the strategic direction of the firm, determine organizational structure, human resource policy and learning culture (Ambrosini, Bowman, & Collier, 2009; Zhang et al., 2009), and play a critical role in garnering loyalty and commitment, changing business strategies and objectives, and achieving efficiency (Gupta & Govindarajan, 1984; Teece, 2007).

From a dynamic capability perspective, the multiple capabilities of a leader based on individual knowledge, education, experience, and skills can effectively influence the way organizations are structured and transformed, assets are renewed and orchestrated, and human resource policies are (re)designed and implemented (Helfat et al., 2007; Helfat & Martin, 2015; Kabanoff & Brown, 2008). Leaders, as a key constituent of SPM, selectively gain and absorb knowledge, reflectively learn and think, and creatively set management philosophy, principles and practices (Tsui, Zhang & Chen, 2017), to dynamically drive strategy formulation and influence strategy implementation which conditions the pattern of behaviors, skills, and knowledge that employees bring to the firm (Jackson & Schuler, 1995; Buller & McEvoy, 2012).

In the new VUCA contexts like high tech industries and fast-growing emerging markets, leaders and managers are often key individuals to interact with the dynamic environment. An example could be the tech war between China and the US, where many large multinationals' CEOs are watching closely to adjust their decision on whether and how to invest and deal with global market strategy. Their capability to sense and capture key trends and ability to access and learn through diverse sources such as networks is critical to set direction for the organization to move forward, via both internal and external knowledge sharing, diffusion, conversion and creation and innovation (Liu & Zhang, 2014; Kremer et al., 2018). While leaders need to be transformational and transactional to lead or adapt in a highly dynamic context (Lopez-Cabrales et al., 2017), the transformational leadership especially contributes to organizational effectiveness (Lowe et al., 1996) in this new context, making organizations more innovative and adaptable (Kang, Solomon, & Choi, 2015). Instead of merely being an asset per se, transformational leaders trigger the overall organizational capability embedded in human beings, and invigorate all stakeholders related to the organization, empowering followers to self-manage and self-develop (Pawar & Eastman, 1997) to learn, be creative, and innovate in an uncertain dynamic environment. CEO's transformational leadership has an impact on

corporate entrepreneurship through risk propensity and decentralizing responsibilities and decision making (Ling, Simsek, Lubatkin, & Veiga, 2008) to prompt strategy formulation through front line managers. Leaders are also responsible for establishing and seizing organizational culture to create and promote organizational identity and loyalty (Augier & Teece, 2009), including entrepreneurial, learning and innovative culture.

4.2. Culture

The link between strategy, people management, and organizational culture is a neglected area of research (Buller & McEvoy, 2012; Molineux, 2013) even though organizational culture is a key factor of the internal organizational environment and has a great bearing on strategic issues (Jackson et al., 2014). While HRM serves to attract, retain, motivate, develop, and use human resources in a firm (Coff, 1997; Kamoche, 1996), organizational culture serves to mobilize, allocate, and leverage resources in achieving company goals through values, rituals, behaviors, management systems, decision criteria, and visionary planning (Barney, 1986). It is especially highlighted in new highly dynamic contexts with elevated ambiguity and volatile levels, where culture is considered as the foundation on which dynamic capabilities are built (Teece, 2014a) to mutually reinforce leadership effects with strategy management (Zhang et al., 2009). Various leaders of Chinese technology firms including Alibaba, Lenovo, Huawei, and Tencent have emphasized the importance of corporate culture to navigate in the new competitive context of emerging markets with dynamic, changeable and uncertain business environment (Tsui et al., 2017; Zhang & Zhou, 2015; Zhang-Zhang et al., 2020).

In brief, culture as a key SPM composition emphasizes external knowledge acquisition and creation to learn and innovate, as well as internal knowledge sharing and participative management to facilitate internal change and innovation. Wright et al. (2001) claim that people management systems may create cultures or mindsets to enable the uniqueness of capabilities

and sustain them. A learning-developmental oriented culture is important to adjust to shifting business demands in a dynamic business environment and equip knowledge workers for this constant transformation (Zhang & Albrecht, 2010). Considering learning as a knowledge internalization process (Chirico & Salvato, 2016; Liu et al., 2020), facilitates not only the creation of future strategic alternatives based on internally generated or externally acquired knowledge, but also the creation of capabilities that continually track, align with or provoke the changing marketplace (Brockbank, 1999; Zhang & Albrecht, 2010). This is why Barney (1986) suggests corporate culture as a set of core values about how to treat multiple stakeholders such as employees, customers, suppliers and others to foster innovativeness and flexibility in firms, leading to sustained superior financial performance.

While the conceptualization of culture is complex (Kroeber & Kluckhohn, 1952; Rohlfer & Zhang, 2016), organizational culture is often built upon the tension between external adaptation and internal integration (Denison & Mishra, 1995) to make knowledge flow. In proposing people management practices to foster knowledge sharing, Cabrera and Cabrera (2005: 724) suggest culture as a key factor with following elements: knowledge-sharing norms, culture of caring (trust and cooperation), high band-width communication, egalitarianism, fairness and perceived support.

Since innovation lies at the heart of organizational knowledge creation (Tushman, 1997) organizational culture needs to be innovation-learning oriented (Brettel & Cleven, 2011; Cerne et al., 2012) to make knowledge the basis of a dynamically developmental firm. Culture reacts to the external environment and its changing conditions and demands and an innovation-learning oriented culture is open, adaptable, and developmental, suitable to encourage continuous learning, sensing, and exploring opportunities in the new and dynamic external environment. The organization must be willing to accept the demands for incessant learning and improvement and the risks associated with VUCA contexts and have values in place to

facilitate the change that leaders initiate (Calori & Sarnin, 1991; Denison & Mishra, 1995). Internally, organizational culture enables coordinated interactions among different units inside an organization to effectively learn, transfer and generate knowledge, tolerating a hyper ambiguous context where uncertain is certain. Core cultural values are widely shared within an organization through basic common assumptions to interact internally and externally among different groups of interest to ensure efficiency, productivity, and smooth coordination possible (Meglino & Ravlin, 1998).

4.3. Learning

Learning has gained managerial emphasis as a source of dynamic capability for sustainable competitive advantages (Teece, 2007, 2014b; Zollo & Winter, 2002) due to its embedded capability to absorb, exchange, and regenerate knowledge through agents of knowledge, that are knowledge workers. Liu and Zhang (2014) illustrate the learning processes of Taiwanese IT firms to dynamically form and enhance innovation capability overtime in the volatile and uncertain sector in an emerging economy context, to acquire, transfer, diffuse and generate knowledge, converting themselves from learners to teachers in specific fields. While Teece et al. (1997: 518) denote organizational competencies partly as “patterns of current practice and learning”, Zhang et al. (2009) empirically identify learning as one of the dynamic elements for vigorously managing people strategically in the new international uncertain context along with leadership. In addition, leaders’ managerial ability arises from prior learning and experience to identify strategic opportunities, to modify operating routines, and to create, extend, and alter the resource and knowledge base of an organization (Helfat et al., 2007). This is empirically confirmed through research by Liu and Zhang (2014) and Liu et al. (2020) with the latter testing the internet marketing capabilities to improve international market performance through the

strategic orientation and knowledge internalization-learning by emerging market Taiwanese firms.

Learning consists of different activities at various levels which also interacts across levels (Liu & Zhang, 2014). Verreyne et al. (2016) suggest the higher or second-order capabilities as dynamic learning capabilities, involving coordination, learning and strategic competitive response activities. In comparison with tacitly understood or explicitly claimed commonly shared innovation-learning oriented culture, the learning element in SPM needs to be specific to act on knowledge brokering like knowledge articulation and codification (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Zander & Kogut, 1995), with the aims to identify new solutions (Zott, 2003), pursue new initiatives (Van den Bosch, Volberda, & De Boer, 1999) and generate new thinking (Henderson & Cockburn, 1994).

Learning as a dynamic capability can take various forms (Helfat et al., 2007), including explorative and exploitative learning (March, 1991). Both explorative and exploitative learning are relevant in strategically managing people and their knowledge in VUCA contexts. While explorative learning addresses the creation of knowledge that does not exist in the firm yet but potentially serves for firms' effectiveness and future direction guiding; exploitative learning is the refinement and update of existing knowledge suitable in efficiency and gradual improvement to complement explorative learning. Hence, in VUCA contexts, management needs to utilize the acquisition, development, and redeployment of people to learn, build, and renew resources and knowledge as well as to reconfigure them in order to innovate, lead, and respond to changes in the market (Teece, 2018). It is a long process for any strategic matter to take effects. However, critical incidences like the 2008 financial crisis or the 2019 pandemic suggest that those who had better strategic management in place were more likely to survive and continue performing during and after the crises event (Zhang-Zhang & Varma, 2020).

Innovative learning behaviors contribute to exploring new ideas and solutions, and driving strategy formulation processes with knowledge generation. As Helfat et al. (2007: 5) claim, “a dynamic capability for learning frequently helps to extend or modify dynamic as well as operational capabilities of all types”. This shows that learning as a pertaining component of SPM possesses an active and evolving property that may transcend the knowledge and capability base. Continuous learning and training constitute part of a dynamic people capability to contribute to strategy formulation in uncertain environments (Zhang et al., 2009).

4.4. Networking

In the new context of highly dynamic VUCA environments, knowledge and capabilities are not always available beforehand, and firms cannot boast they possess all required resources and capabilities to achieve and sustain their competitive advantage. Even glorious multinationals like GE and GM did stumble. Technology- and knowledge-intensive sectors with strategic alliances and collaborations between organizations are illustrative examples of the relevance of networking which has become a recognized strategic organizational response to these turbulent and rapid changes in new business environments (Cravens, Piercy & Shipp, 1996). Consequently, network ties (Tajeddini, Martin & Ali, 2020), interorganizational partnerships or alliances are part of strategic issues to access, transfer or co-create knowledge and enhance innovation in the new dynamic environments like the alliance learning that Liu and Zhang (2014) exemplify. In such socially complex relationships, people management systems play an important role in the promotion and maintenance of those interorganizational partnerships via trust, knowledge sharing and teamwork (Wright et al., 2001).

Mergers and acquisitions, strategic alliances, and open innovation systems are accepted strategic options for acquiring and accessing quickly new resources, knowledge, and capabilities. Learning and knowledge transfer through different forms of knowledge

conversions (i.e., Nonaka's SECI model) not only occurs within an organization, but also among organizations within the network to enhance strategic capability (Liu & Zhang, 2014; Sirén, 2012). The network structure among people plays here a critical role in order to gain access to these valuable external sources at a fast pace in both a closed system, e.g., within organizational boundaries, as well as in an open system, which seems to be particularly relevant in technologically advanced societies and the digital era nowadays.

Technology-based businesses like Fintechs operate in an eco-systematic way rather than as independent units. They are strongly embedded into the Fintech ecosystem that interacts with the larger business ecosystem, in which the role of stakeholders and sector boundaries are fuzzy and ambiguous (Zhang-Zhang et al., 2020). Networking thus becomes part of an organization's social capital that connects individuals represented by particular structural connections, relational bonds, and cognitive understanding (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 1998). It is especially beneficial for new strategic contexts like volatile and uncertain internet-related businesses, and ambiguous and complex high-context culture environments. Successful Asian emerging market firms are said to be characterized by these networks to achieve their superior business performance, relying not only on Guanxi in Chinese business contexts (Chen, Chen & Huang, 2013), but also on Korean Chaebol (Kim 2005), or Japanese Keiretsu (McGuire & Dow, 2009) when their businesses first emerged. The booming e-commerce or social media businesses are fundamentally built on the bases of networks that connect buyers, sellers, and different informants, often small-sized enterprises, or simply registered individual users, thereby enabling them to compete against big multinationals through economies of scale facilitated by powerful platforms (Zhang-Zhang et al., 2020). Alibaba, Amazon and Facebook are some of these platforms, where knowledge and innovation are transferred and created across sectors among different stakeholders accelerating the degree of environmental dynamism.

Network configurations are commonly differentiated into three types of relational archetypes and characteristics (Kang, Morris, & Snell, 2007; Methot, Rosado-Solomon & Allen, 2018): entrepreneurial, architectural, and functional. While all network configurations encompass social capital embedded in people to create knowledge as the basis for firms to dynamically evolve, the entrepreneurial archetype network emphasizes the weak ties with non-redundant actors that enable spontaneity in actions (Kang et al., 2007) for strategic connection, influence, learning absorption, and proposing initiatives. Non-redundant weak ties with external parties do not present a strong group norm that strictly regulates individual actions; instead, they allow sufficient flexibility for individuals to adapt to dynamic environments (Leana & Van Buren, 1999). Weak ties to a broad, outreaching network bring novel and non-redundant information and knowledge to the firm (Burt, 1992; Granovetter, 1973), which are an important input for people to make informed and innovative strategic decisions. Such an entrepreneurial social network structure is advantageous for exploring novel and different knowledge (Kang et al., 2007), creating platforms and ecosystems for sustainable competitive advantages (Zhang-Zhang et al., 2020). Architectural networks, by contrast, resemble the inter-connectedness among units in organizations (Kang et al., 2007), and emphasize cross-functional cooperation to facilitate change initiation besides functional cooperation. Finally, a functional network structure is strong with dense, cooperative ties among employees of the same function who share norms and trust (Kang et al., 2007). A cooperative and collaborative culture, ties and networks would prevent deviation from strategic execution (Uzzi, 1997), facilitate the sharing and integration of in-depth knowledge (Kang et al., 2007) especially with tacit knowledge in the socialization mode (Nonaka, 1991; Zhang et al., 2013), and prompt exploitative innovation (Jansen et al., 2006).

5. THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

Contemporary new business contexts characterized by high levels of uncertainty and pace of change are accelerated by disruptive technological advancements, the rising power of emerging market firms, and the simultaneously happening multilevel events such as the COVID-19 induced pandemic and economic crises. This has placed people in the center of attention to extend further the RBV and KBV theorization and to generate new knowledge and capabilities for strategic direction setting.

Viewing people management as a more encompassing term, Wright et al. (2001) expand the relevant practices to those beyond the control of the HR function, embracing communication, culture, leadership and a host of others impacting employee behavior and shaping their competencies, attitudes and motivations. However, as others, Wright et al.'s (2001) vision on people management practices is still based on strategic HRM, which is rooted in HRM practices to bridge knowledge management and dynamic capabilities. Jolink and Dankbaar (2010), by contrast, prefer using the term 'people management' with the desire to go beyond the traditional consideration of HRM in their study of inter-organizational networking. The impact of people management practices associated with networking behavior and other knowledge management processes is likely to be stronger if they are applied as a system of mutually reinforcing practices (Jolink & Dankbaar, 2010; Wright et al., 2001). We posit SPM to extend the RBV and KBV beyond human resources to include a range of stakeholders within and outside of the organizational network, to collaborate under an innovative learning culture for the dynamic management of knowledge acquisition, transfer, conversion and creation.

SPM develops the competencies and capabilities through the four dynamic drivers of knowledge sources if we recognize that the inimitability of these capabilities stems from unobservability, ambiguity, and complexity (Wright et al., 2001). The human role is more important in the context of a highly dynamic and uncertain environment where existing routines play a less dominant role (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000) and existing structure-oriented processes

may lead to dysfunctional decisions (Covaleski & Dirsmith, 1981). Compared with other types of resources and capabilities, people-related knowledge and capabilities can purposefully alter and dynamize the resource and knowledge base of an organization. Though having provided relevant guidance on the role that individuals play in performance, strategic HRM has missed much of the organizational view of knowledge and deviated from the original strategic purpose of its foundation (Wright et al., 2001; Jackson et al., 2014).

Indeed, SPM covers this gap by holistically integrating the dynamic processes of leadership, culture, learning, and networking, which can be particularly applied in the new context of VUCA environments as an extension of the RBV and KBV. This process is accomplished by deploying resources and capsuling both explicit processes and tacit elements such as know-how and leadership (Wang & Ahmed, 2007) through different knowledge conversion forms, including socialization, externalization, combination and internalization (SECI). Also learning to reconfigure and transform processes (Teece et al., 1997) and applying distinct strategies in different capability-development stages and contexts (Branzei & Vertinsky, 2006) are key. In these processes, non-managerial individuals identified as knowledge workers impact on dynamic capabilities via their day-to-day actions within and around the organization to advance and improve streamline processes (Salvato, 2009). Kidwants' CEO and the hot-pot restaurant chain Haidilao stress that their frontline employees are the ones who learn what customers want, interact with them and lead the process to generate new and creative ideas (Tsui et al., 2017, Wu & Zhang, 2015).

Therefore, the paper's contributions are threefold. 1) We explicitly distinguish dynamic environments' associated features and identify three commonly addressed new contexts of highly dynamic environment: technology-intensive or -disrupted dynamic context, high-velocity emerging market context, and crisis-induced unpredictable environments. Moreover, we pinpoint the potential cross-level and multiple sources induced environmental dynamism. 2)

We extend the RBV and KBV by explicitly differentiating the conceptualization of people management from HRM, with the former proposed as the dynamic capability generator, taking the knowledge worker perspective proposed by the founder of the knowledge school, Prof. Ikujiro Nonaka. 3) We propose a holistic SPM framework for further exploration of people-centric knowledge creation in the new contexts of highly dynamic environments for sustainable performance that is undergoing its paradigmatic shift, with four dynamic constituents identified, including leadership, culture, learning and networking.

Future Research Directions

The paper's contributions offer several potential future research lines which we discuss briefly and for which we develop relevant propositions to help their development. First, there is a need to further clarify the conceptualization of new contexts of dynamic environment; its causes and features are not always as clear as it should be. We posit this conceptual work within the new context for the theoretical extension of the RBV and KBV. Although we identify three types inducing highly dynamic VUCA contexts, we also find the complexity to trace these effects in an explicit way when these effects are multiple-sourced across levels. Scholars have been deploying environmental dynamism as research contexts for decades, but the newer contemporary contexts have a more accelerated changing pace, more profound and prolonged impacts, and more complex consequences, especially with the simultaneous effects from technology, emerging markets and crises (Fletcher-Brown et al., 2021; Malik et al., 2021; Zhang-Zhang et al., 2020). A systematic review of dynamic environments' contextualization could help striving towards a consensus on these definitions and categorizations. This would be meaningful for a better understanding and exploration of these relatively new contexts, their causes, effects and processes. Scholars could also empirically examine whether the knowledge

worker perspective works better in highly dynamic VUCA contexts than in a relatively stable or predictable context. As such, we propose:

P1: All else being equal, while the knowledge worker perspective will work equally well in a dynamic VUCA environment or a relatively stable environment, the SPM approach will function better when the degree of environmental dynamism is higher.

Relatedly, the four dynamic SPM capability constituents could be unbundled to identify their individual effects in the new contexts of highly dynamic VUCA environment with diverse research directions. We propose some sub-proposition which denote illustrative but not exhaustive research lines:

P1.1: While all leaders need to develop their dynamic capabilities to adjust in the new contexts, transformational leaders will function better in a highly dynamic VUCA environment than transactional leaders.

P1.2: In a highly dynamic context, an innovation-learning oriented culture will be more effective than a control-cost oriented culture.

P1.3: In a dynamic environment, explorative learning will allow firms to better enhance their capabilities in sustaining long term performance than will do exploitative learning.

P1.4: An entrepreneurial network will add more value than architectural and functional networks in a new dynamic context.

Next, the original contribution of Prof. Nonaka in founding the knowledge school is based on the studies of Japanese companies, which are largely people-centric albeit their transformation over decades. Though the knowledge school's principles are widespread today, the people-centricity in Japan was generated during its emerging economy period and has been maintained in its advanced economy state. Given the importance of understanding the context (e.g., national culture) in people-related matters (see, e.g., DeNisi et al., 2021), we believe that

the applicability and generalizability of the knowledge worker perspective should be empirically investigated as follows:

P2: While the knowledge worker perspective functions in various national contexts, national values moderate the degree of easiness with which SPM can be successfully implemented.

P2.1: In the competitive new dynamic context of digitalization, the contribution by lower-level knowledge workers to firm performance will be higher in a low power-distance country than a high-power distance one.

P2.2: Among emerging market competitors, firms from countries with strong learning traditions and culture flexibility will perform better than others by dynamizing their people and knowledge management capabilities.

P2.3: In contemporary VUCA context, knowledge workers in a low uncertainty-avoidance national culture will have better innovation performance compared to their counterparts in a high uncertainty-avoidance culture.

P2.4: Firms with strong entrepreneurial, learning and innovation culture will offset national conservative culture characterized by high power distance and uncertainty avoidance to sustain performance via SPM.

Relatedly, given the complexities involved in effectuating SPM based configurations of knowledge workers, further research is required to understand the degree to which the dynamic constituents of SPM would holistically combine better for sustainable purposes in new dynamic contexts such as high-velocity emerging markets. Since the unique combination of the key elements (leadership, culture, learning, networking), can make firms more agile to adapt to or influence external forces, we propose the following:

P3: Firms will adapt better to dynamic environments when the dynamic constituents of SPM are integrated and bundled rather than being unconnected. In addition, this effect will be

more evident in a complex high-degree-dynamism environment with multiple sourced inducers in which it is harder to trace the explicit causes, processes and effects of the occurrences.

Finally, we conceptualize SPM as a much broader concept, relative to the traditional strategic HRM in extending the RBV and KBV theorization. Though technology & communication and HR practices are not principal constituents for dynamic SPM, they play an important role as both hard and soft infrastructures for the organizational functioning and are part of the organizability factor in the RBV framework of VRIO: being valuable, rare, inimitable, and organizable. Technology plays its contribution to knowledge management systems (Chirico & Salvato, 2016), innovative and learning cultures, and social networks (Cabrera & Cabrera, 2005). Alternative HR practices mutually reinforce policies by relating to critical features of dynamic capabilities for knowledge management and complementing leadership behavior and organizational climate in a broadened people management conceptualization (Purcell & Hutchison, 2007; Purcell & Kinnie, 2006). As well, empowered employees will take more initiatives to participate in the knowledge absorption, transfer, and creation process as true knowledge workers and become distributed leaders. On the contrary, employees may behave with resistance, knowledge hiding, and rejection. Pereira and Mohiya (2021) echo the general theorization and identify that a positive and open organizational environment combined with positive individual intention will encourage knowledge sharing and reduce knowledge hiding in a Saudi multinational company context. Though knowledge hiding behavior may be expected to amplify in a VUCA context due to disruptive condition and diminishing psychological contract (Soares & Mosquera, 2019; Rousseau, Hansen & Tomprou, 2018), we believe that incorporating dynamic constituents of SPM and HRM best practices would help offset and strengthen the knowledge management process, as would the effective intervention of communication and technology for knowledge sharing. As such, we propose:

P4: SPM configurations that use HR best practices as well as communication and technology as back-up mechanisms will be more effective than those that do not. We would also expect these supporting infrastructures to have complementary effects with the main constituents' systematic effects indicated in P3.

Managerial Implications

Our proposed framework also has implications for the management of a firm's internal workforce. First, approaching SPM from the RBV and KBV of the firm, the workforce's scalability is a requirement for firms operating in dynamic environments (Dyer & Ericksen, 2005; 2006). As such, it is critical, even more so in a highly dynamic environment, that managers create and foster a culture that allows the organization to switch between HR configurations at short notice. The culture should further encourage and support entrepreneurship, innovation, continuous learning, and self-initiated transformation. Relatedly, the organization's knowledge workers should be empowered to proactively seek solutions by including their social networks into the organization's existing networks.

Next, dynamic SPM may also influence workforce fluidity, the speed and ease of transitions in the HR configuration. Under new disruptive, innovative, and VUCA contexts, value chains and human capitals may require reconfiguration and redeployment, to allow firms to acquire or spinoff certain structures and human resources at a fast pace. Recombined and reconfigured strategic people and human resources need to have better capability to formulate and implement different strategies appropriate to diverse, competitive, and turbulent new environments and to detect new opportunities (Camps et al., 2016). In a personal conversation, J.C. Spender suggested three types of uncertainties based on Knightian analysis: ignorance of universe and of what is judged knowable; indeterminacy – my not being able to know what you are going to do Y when I do X, and if I don't fully know my own mind; and incommensurability

– all knowledge is captured in language and languages are plural and differ. In our current framework, we have mainly targeted SPM to address new VUCA contexts. The intrinsic uncertainties suggest reinforcement of the people-centric innovation, given the inherent uncertainty and ambiguity embedded in the human being and knowledge per se.

Accordingly, managers should be appropriately equipped to work with complex people and knowledge systems and be ready and able to build innovative business ecosystem, which would be crucial for the sustainable development of the firm. Concerning HR professionals, business professionals hardly see them as strategic partners because they lack the bottom-line perspective and fail to prioritize work that supports business objectives and targets (Gao, Zhang, Zhao, Li & Wu, 2016). SPM provides a broadly defined conceptualization and framework relevant to make the role of people more inclusive compared to strategic HRM. HR professionals are the critical partners who need a comprehensive understanding of the firm's business and business fundamentals to be able to contribute proactively to strategic management. Hence, it is critical to add business acumen into the HR specialization. Another option is to locate business professionals to the HR department, as did BBVA, which was ranked as the most innovative multinational bank globally by The Banker in 2018. SPM professionals need to have strategic acumen as well as cross-functional expertise of the business to fully mobilize people and human capital to initiate strategic changes (Becker & Huselid, 2006; Ulrich, 2016). “Extensive and frequent use of prototyping, real-time information, experimentation, and multiple alternatives” (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000: 1113) are required in high-velocity environments and the firm may well be particularly reliant on the sensing and seizing instincts and actions of the top management team (Teece, 2014a). This will give an opportunity to HR professionals to become strategic partners.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Our framework specifies the nature and constituents of SPM, focusing on its abilities in driving strategic direction in the new dynamic business environments. This is a fruitful line of research that extends the theory of the RBV and KBV and blends the literature on knowledge management for the dynamic theory of the firm and SPM, to align consistently with and effectively influence the firm's strategy and with changes in the opportunities and requirements afforded by the new business environment (Teece, 2014a; 2018). SPM's conceptualization builds the foundation for further empirical research on the embeddedness of people management systems along these variables, rather than simply and independently controlling for them in research. It will help understand better when, where, and why human resources and their management dynamically ally and co-evolve with strategy (Jackson et al., 2014; Paauwe, 2009; Wright & Snell, 1998) while capturing the dynamism in the process in the new contexts.

Such encompassing focus in SPM research provides an impetus for examining the timing of the coevolution of SPM with strategy's planning, decisions making, and implementation (Wright & Snell, 1998) and better data on the time frame to reflect SPM capabilities and schemes. This exploration can move people management and knowledge management researchers towards a much richer understanding of the balancing role of SPM capabilities in the link with strategy, and extend RBV and KBV.

We applied a broadly defined people-centered approach to extend RBV and KBV, and address the knowledge basis of a dynamic firm to fill the gap existing in strategic HRM (Jackson et al., 2014) in the new VUCA contexts, by incorporating four dynamic people-related constitutes into the framework - leadership, culture, learning, and networking, and two complementary elements: innovative human resource practices, and communication & technology. Instead of considering them as exogenous factors related to strategic HRM, we call to treat them as part of the pertaining elements of dynamic SPM. The proposed framework is

amenable for a new dynamic strategic context and how these SPM configurations coevolve with business strategy under a knowledge management perspective.

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Table 1: Inter-relationship between People Management and Human Resource Management

Similarity level

Theoretical Advancement Level

Low

Prospective: People management has been given a broader definition implicitly in comparison with HRM, though authors have not explicitly distinguished these conceptual differences, e.g.,
 *Saini and Budhwar (2008): While the title is ‘Managing the human resource,’ the abstract heavily uses people management (3 times). In the main body of the text, ‘people management’ is used 16 times implicitly giving a broader meaning and context to managing people in an emerging market SME context;
 * Purcell and Hutchinson (2007) use people management for these roles that front-line managers (FLMs) play to deliver HR policies and duties, like selecting, appraising, developing and leadership behaviors. People management is thus distinct from HRM as the user is FLMs rather than HR professionals, even though the functions are essentially identical.

Differentiator: The term “people management” is used to differentiate HRM by expanding its scope to function on strategic issues such as knowledge management and social networking. Though HR practices are included as part of people management, the essential focus differs, e.g.,
 * People management is used with the intent to go beyond the traditional understanding of HRM and its control to create a climate for fostering inter-organizational networking (Jolink & Danbaar, 2010);
 * Though many HR practices (e.g., compensation and rewards) are included as part of people management practices, Cabrera and Cabrera (2005) distinguished people management practices from HR practices essentially by adding two more elements: culture and technology with their sub-elements such as communication and cultural-fit IT, to foster knowledge sharing.

Low **Old Wine, New Bottle:** People management is the term used to attract attention. However, there are no substantial differences with HRM, e.g.,
 * "People management" is used in the title and the term 'people' appeared several times in the abstract (2) and text (5), but the main concepts are from HRM with the term "HR" frequently used in the text (32) (Wilkinson et al., 2014);
 * Similarly, Alagaraja et al. (2015), who used the term “people management” following a literature review on human resource development, without providing any specific distinction.

Progressive: People management is identical to HRM but represents the theoretical advancement from personnel management, e.g.,
 *Caldwell (2002): 'People management professionals' is used to refer to HRM which is highlighted in change management interventions, in comparison to personnel management;
 * Stockard (1980): People management is used in the title and human resource function in the subtitle. These suggest their differentiation from personnel management, though critics (e.g., Summer, 1980) have argued that the content still addresses personnel management.

High

Table 2. People management and human resource management comparison

	People Management	Human Resource Management
Management Philosophy	People are central as a value adding source for the long-term growth and survival of the organization	Exploitation and exploration of human beings as resources and assets for the success of financial results
Conceptualization	A broad definition of managing people in organizations and even beyond the organizational boundary for firm's long-term sustainability	A specific definition of managing human resources within the organization through established HR department and professionals for firm performance
Strategic orientation	Sustainability oriented	Performance oriented
Target audience	Managers and stakeholders at different levels in the ecosystem	Organization's HR professionals
Key actors	Stakeholders, leaders, frontline managers, HR professionals, employees	HR professionals, employees
Subject of action	General manager, frontline manager, and divisional manager including HR manager act on all organizational members and other stakeholders	HR managers and department act on other managers and employees
Dynamic capability elements	Leadership, culture, learning, networking, HR best practices, communication & technology	Job design, staffing, training & development, performance appraisal, compensation & rewards
Applicable organizational contexts	Highly dynamic contexts where people creativity can help firms in navigating through uncertainties, ambiguity, and complexity	Relatively stable contexts where strategy planning is feasible, and HR can align with context to implement strategy

